

First Record of *Courtesius Illuminates* Distant (Hemiptera: Pyrrhocoridae) from India

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ABSTRACT

Courtesius illuminates Distant is being recorded for the first time from India. *C. illuminates* has been re-described along with additional diagnostic characters based on measurements. Diagnostic characters of genus *Courtesius* Distant have also been given in brief.

Key words : Hemiptera, Pyrrhocoridae, *Courtesius illuminates*.

INTRODUCTION

Less explored genus *Courtesius* Distant of the family Pyrrhocoridae are of moderate size (about 5 - 6 m.m. long), reddish brown in colour with yellow, white and black markings, mimic ants by virtue of its body colour, shape of the head and antennae. Genus *Courtesius* is represented by only five species throughout the world, out of which, two species (*C. stysi* Ahmad and Zaidi, *C. quinquisignatus* Blote) are recorded from India and one each from Pakistan (*C. pakistanensis* Ahmad and Zaidi), Myanmar (*C. illuminates* Distant) and Nepal (*C. nepalensis* Stehlik) (Ahmad and Zaidi, 1990; Stehlik, 2003). All members of genus *Courtesius* exhibit brachypterous form of wings. During the course the present study we recorded *C. illuminatus* for the first time from India and re-described with additional diagnostic characters. However, the presumably high biodiversity of the Oriental Pyrrhocorids are still insufficiently known and many undescribed taxa are still awaiting discovery.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The description of *Courtesius illuminates* Distant was based on two specimens belonging to the National Zoological Collection, Zoological Survey of India, Kolkata. Specimens were identified, measurements and photographs was taken with the help of stereoscopic microscope (Leica M 205A).

RESULTS

Genus *Courtesius* Distant

1904. *Courtesius* Distant, *Fauna Brit. India, Rhynchota*, 2: 114.

Member of the genus *Courtesius* can easily be recognized by having ovate body, head more or less triangular, wider than anterior margin of pronotum, eyes large, sessile, laterally bulging, antennae with first joint shorter than head and not equal to 3rd joint, pronotum with lateral margins laminate, hemelytra abbreviated, membrane absent, legs normal, Fore femora of both sexes robust, basally narrowed, its dorsal margin in both sexes with three distant teeth spaced along nearly entire length of femur (except of apices) Fore tibiae straight, without

postero-ventral denticles. Male genitalia with blade of the paramere pointed at apex.

***Courtesius illuminates* Distant**

1904. *Courtesius illuminates*: Distant, *Fauna Brit. India, Rhynchota*, **2**: 114.

1990. *Courtesius illuminates*: Ahmed and Zaidi, *Annotationes Zoologicae et Botanicae*, (196): 1-11.

Type species: *Courtesius illuminatus* Distant.

Material examined: 2 exs., Dharampur, Alt., 5000 ft. Solan Dist., W. Himalayas, 20.v.1913, coll. Phaku Ram, (Reg. no. 5522/H7).

Colour: Body reddish brown, lateral margins of pronotum and apical margins of corium pale luteous; first joint of antennae beneath, lateral margins of pro-sternum, trochanters, base of anterior and intermediate and basal half of posterior femora pale luteous.

Head triangular from anterior view, wider than long, length 0.60 X to its width; eyes prominent, bulging and semi-spherical in shape; antennae distinctly longer than half of the body length, length of antennal segments, A1:A2:A3:A4: :18:23:15:24, basal joint slightly curved, antennal formula, $3 < 1 < 2 < 4$, basal labial segment almost reaching to the posterior margin of the head; rostrum four segmented, reaching posterior coxae, basal two joints as long as head and pronotum together.

Pronotum wider than long, width of pronotum 1.61 X to its length, trapezoidal with lateral margins laminate, anterior angle rounded and posterior margin straight. Anterior half of pronotum convexed, slightly depressed towards posterior half. Scent glands are highly developed and complex. Fore femora thickened and incrassate, shorter than maximum width of pronotum, hind femora slightly longer than head and pronotum together, tibiae and tarsal segments, in all three legs are provided with spines arranged in row, basal joints of tarsi longer than rest of the tarsal joints; scutellum more or less triangular, about as long as broad; corium coarsely punctuate, length of corium longer than the length of pronotum and slightly

shorter than its width, reaching the third abdominal segment. Abdomen ovate, wider than the maximum width of head in middle, about 1.19 X to hind femora and rounded apically.

Figure-1A-C. *Courtesius illuminates*: A. Dorsal View (Male), B. Head and Thorax (lateral view-Male) and C. Pygophor.

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